

SUMEX DELIVERABLE D6.6

ORDP: OPEN RESEARCH DATA PILOT

Summary:

The SUMEX (Sustainable Management in Extractive Industries) project has taken significant steps to actively engage in a Data Research Pilot as part of its broader mission to establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe.

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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document, distinct from traditional paper deliverables, focuses on the implementation of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) within the SUMEX project. Emphasising the paramount value of transparency, SUMEX actively participates in the dissemination of research data through Zenodo, categorising information into three key groups:

- Public deliverables,
- Presentations, and
- Raw data residing within the SUMEX knowledge repository.

For a more comprehensive understanding, the essential points covered in this document are summarised in the following table:

Topic	Description
Open access to research data	Emphasizing transparency and accessibility
Research data summary	Extracting important research data findings

Furthermore, it's important to note that detailed information on data management has been extensively presented in Deliverable D7.3 "Data Management Plan." As such, this document primarily references the content of that deliverable and avoids redundant repetition. Moreover, all data that are published on Zenodo can also be found the project webpage (sumexproject.eu).

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 PURPOSE OF THE OPEN RESEARCH DATA PILOT

The open research data pilot for SUMEX serves multiple purposes, including promoting transparency, facilitating data sharing, accelerating research, supporting policy development, engaging the public, and enhancing the capabilities of the project's Community of Practice. This open approach to research data aligns with the project's broader mission of sustainability in the extractive industry and contributes to informed decision-making and greater collaboration among different actors and actor groups.

2.2 SCOPE OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The scope of an open research data pilot in SUMEX is designed to align with the overarching goals of the project, which, in this case, is to promote sustainable management focusing on Europe. It involves a combination of research data collection, research data management, sharing, analysis, engagement, and capacity-building activities, all aimed at facilitating evidence-based decision-making and transparency in the extractive industry.

2.3 RELATED DOCUMENTS

This document is mainly related to the Data Management Plan (DMP, Deliverable D7.3), which has been submitted in April 2021.

3 OPEN ACCESS TO RESEARCH DATA

With the introduction of the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP), the Commission intended to improve access and reuse of research data used in H2020 projects.

The ORDP is mainly used in the context of research data to empirically support the results presented in scientific publications. According to the H2020 online Manual, ORDP refers to the right of access and reuse of digital research data to the terms and conditions set out in the Grant Agreement. In the research context, these data include, but are not limited to, statistics, results from experiments, measurements, observations related to field investigations, survey results, interview recordings, and visual materials.

In principle, a distinction is made mainly between two different types of data:

- **Underlying data:** Data needed to validate the results presented in the scientific publications, including the associated metadata.
- **Other data:** For instance, curated data not directly attributable to a publication, or raw data, as specified in the DMP.

3.1 APPLICATION OF ORDP IN SUMEX

SUMEX is a Coordination and Support action with the main objective to support a common understanding of what sustainability means for the extractive sector along the extractive value chain (i.e. prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities) with the set-up of a [sustainability framework](#) focused on Europe. Furthermore, this framework is intended to contribute to improve the permitting procedure, to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other actors in seizing this opportunity.

The SUMEX sustainability framework is applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas (i.e. socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration). This is done to identify or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. The CoP will consider relevant actor groups, with a focus on permitting authorities and policy makers related to mineral extraction, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars.

In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the extractive sector.

3.1.1 Datasets containing sensitive, personal data and privacy protocols

Montanuniversität Leoben (as Coordinator) together with the other SUMEX partners took care that no sensitive data that might have infringed IPR or GDPR have been published.

Literature review and previous existing information/documents on other (similar) projects or best practice cases will not be subject to the ORDP because this material was not created during the project.

3.2 REQUIREMENTS OF THE OPEN RESEARCH DATA PILOT

Requirement 1: The project has to deposit the research data in an open data repository. SUMEX uses Zenodo (see description below) for this purpose, which allows researchers to store both publications and research data and to link them with each other.

Requirement 2: In this context, projects must allow third parties not only to have access to this research data, but also to mine, evaluate, exploit, reproduce and disseminate (free of charge for any user) this research data. One straightforward and effective way of doing this is to attach Creative Commons Licences (CCBY or CC0) to the data deposited.

Zenodo: Zenodo is an open catch-all research data repository that enables researchers, scientists, EU projects and institutions to share research results, regardless of size or format. Free to upload and free to access, it makes scientific outputs of all kinds citable, shareable and discoverable for the long term.

Zenodo is harvested by the OpenAIRE portal and hosted by the CERN cloud infrastructure. <https://zenodo.org/>

4 SUMMARY OF RESEARCH DATA

This section provides an overview of data generated in the SUMEX project and their purpose.

4.1 DATA-DRIVEN SUSTAINABILITY FRAMEWORK

SUMEX's participation in the Data Research Pilot is an integral part of its objective to create a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. This framework is designed to align with key sustainability initiatives, including the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, and EU Social License to Operate considerations. The project acknowledges the importance of data in measuring and assessing sustainability progress across these areas.

4.2 INCORPORATING DATA FROM VARIOUS SOURCES

In the Data Research Pilot, SUMEX was actively working to incorporate data from diverse sources, including industry, government, academia, and civil society. This multifaceted approach ensures that the data analysis is comprehensive, providing a more accurate representation of the industry's sustainability landscape.

4.3 DATA ANALYSIS ACROSS THE EXTRACTIVE VALUE CHAIN

The data research efforts of SUMEX extend across the entire extractive value chain, covering prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, and post-closure activities. Data is examined in the context of five core focus areas, including socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics, and permitting policy integration. This comprehensive approach ensures that data-driven insights can inform improvements at every stage of the value chain.

4.4 DEVELOPMENT OF AN OPEN ACCESS DATA REPOSITORY

One of the key outcomes of the Data Research Pilot is the development of an open access [knowledge repository](#). This data repository compiles best practices and data-driven tools that can be utilised by actors in the extractive industry, as well as policy makers. These resources are expected to empower industry players, regulators, and other actors with the knowledge and tools needed to make informed decisions and promote sustainable management.

4.5 CREATION OF A COMMUNITY OF PRACTICE (COP)

In combination with the data research activities, SUMEX is in the process of establishing a Community of Practice (CoP) that brings together relevant actor groups. Notably, permitting authorities and policy makers relevant for the extractive sector from across the EU are a central focus. This digital platform has served as a centre point for collaboration and knowledge sharing, further enhancing the project's data research and sustainability initiatives. A [LinkedIn group](#) is intended to support knowledge exchange and create an open space for discussion.

4.6 ACTOR COLLABORATION

SUMEX actively engages actors from industry, government, academia, and civil society in the Data Research Pilot program. This collaboration ensures that data collection and analysis benefit from diverse perspectives and expertise. The input from these actors contributes to a holistic understanding of the challenges and opportunities in the extractive industry.

4.7 OVERVIEW ON PUBLIC RESEARCH DATA GENERATED IN THE SUMEX PROJECT

Annex I of Deliverable D7.3 describes in great detail what kind of research data is expected to be generated in the SUMEX project and its classification as confidential or as public. All data classified as public are uploaded on the SUMEX project webpage. In addition, a set of public data are also uploaded on Zenodo, divided into three groups:

- Public deliverables,
- Presentations (i.e. good practice cases presented at workshops and conferences), and
- Raw data residing within the SUMEX knowledge repository.

5 CONCLUSION

In summary, SUMEX's active engagement in the Open Research Data Pilot not only promotes data-driven decision-making within the extractive industry but also accelerates the adoption of sustainable practices in this sector. Through the utilisation of research data, SUMEX plays a pivotal role in shaping a robust sustainability framework, facilitating the efforts of policymakers and various actors. This collective effort is a significant stride towards ensuring the sustainable production of minerals in the European Union. Consequently, SUMEX views its involvement in the Open Research Data Pilot as a crucial and impactful stride towards fostering transparency, evidence-based practices, and sustainability within the European extractive industry.

SUMEX BACKGROUND

SUMEX is a 36-months project funded by the EC that started on 01.11.2020. The project supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other actors in seizing this opportunity.

To foster more, but sustainable mineral production in the EU, SUMEX (*SU*stainable Management in *EX*tractive industries) will establish a sustainability framework for the extractive industry in Europe. It does so by considering the Sustainable Development Goals, the European Green Deal, as well as EU Social License to Operate considerations and will involve actors from industry, government, academia and civil society backgrounds from all across the EU.

This framework is then applied across the extractive value chain to analyse the mineral, as well as relevant economic, environmental and social policy frameworks of the EU, member states and selected regions along five focus areas – socio-economic and environmental impact assessments, land use planning, health and safety, reporting official statistics and permitting processes/policy integration-to find, or build, where needed, good practices or tools for an open access toolkit, which will be embedded in a broader Community of Practise (CoP) and which forms the basis for capacity building. This CoP will consider relevant actor groups, with a focus on permitting authorities, across the EU, providing a digital platform and using a series of workshops and webinars. In SUMEX, the experience from other projects builds a powerful foundation for addressing the challenge of how best to implement sustainability considerations into the whole raw materials value chain.

Challenge: No common understanding of sustainable management in extractive industries

SUMEX supports the set-up of a European sustainability framework to improve the permitting procedure along the extractive value chain (prospecting, exploration, extraction, processing, closure, post closure activities), to guarantee timely decisions, a transparent governmental regulatory regime, appealing financial and administrative conditions and sustainable natural environmental and social conditions. The main mission of SUMEX is to assist policymakers and other actors in seizing this opportunity.

Objectives of SUMEX

- Strengthen policy coordination and agenda setting along the mineral extraction value chain;
- Propose a uniform EU sustainable management in extractive industries context;
- Cluster with other projects to identify good practices and good practise principles;
- Identify good practises and principles for policy strategies and strategic approaches, coordination/integration and approaches and property rights regimes for different institutional systems;
- Build a toolkit with good practises, with a focus on access to land, permitting and policy coordination and integration;
- Identify actor learning needs and requirements;
- Deploy an open access toolkit for capacity building across EU and with all actors.

More info on <https://www.sumexproject.eu/>

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